

mixtures. The M.S.P. values in respect of various surfactants, viz. LPC, CPC, CPB, CTAB and CDBAC (cationic); SLS, Manoxol-OT and Tergitol-7 (anionic); and the mixtures, LPC+SLS, LPC+Manoxol-OT, LPC+Tergitol-7; CPC+SLS, CPC+Manoxol-OT, CPC+Tergitol-7, CPB+SLS, CPB+Manoxol-OT, CPB+Tergitol-7, CTAB+SLS, CTAB+Manoxol-OT, CTAB+Tergitol-7, CDBAC+SLS, CDBAC+Manoxol-OT, and CDBAC+Tergitol-7, have been determined and listed in Table 1. A perusal of Table 1 shows that the M.S.P. values in respect of the mixtures, LPC+SLS, LPC+Manoxol-OT, LPC+Tergitol-7, CPC+SLS, CPC+Manoxol-OT, CPC+Tergitol-7, CPB+SLS, CPB+Manoxol-OT, CPB+Tergitol-7, CTAB+SLS, CTAB+Manoxol-OT, CTAB+Tergitol-7, CDBAC+SLS, CDBAC+Tergitol-7 are much larger than those for individual surfactants thereby indicating antagonistic effects of these mixtures in the suppression of the maximum of Ga^{III} . This is further supported by the fact that the values of I_{RT} , in each case, at the concentration of surfactant at which the maximum gets just suppressed are lower for these mixtures than those for individual surfactants.

It is interesting to note that M.S.P. value in respect of the mixture of CDBAC and Manoxol-OT is equal to half of the individual M.S.P. value, thereby indicating that this mixture shows neither additive nor antagonistic effect in suppressing the maximum of Ga^{III} . Further, it is also interesting to note that none of the probable mixtures of the two surfactants (*i.e.* cationic and anionic) shows the additive effect in the suppression of negative polarographic maximum of Ga^{III} .

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References

1. P. ZUMAN and I. M. KOLTHOFF, "Progress in Polarography", Interscience, New York, 1962, Vol. I, p. 88.
2. J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, New York, 1966 p. 299.
3. E. L. COLICHMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4036.
4. W. U. MALIK and R. HAQUE, *J. Polarogr. Soc.*, 1962, **8**, 62.
5. H. J. ANTWEILER, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1937, **43**, 596; 1938, **44**, 719, 888.
6. J. W. GIBBS, *Trans Connecticut Acad.*, 1876, **3**; "Collected Works", 1928, Vol. I, p. 230; J. RICE, "Commentary on the Scientific Writings of Gibbs", Yale University Press, New Haven, 1937, Vol. I.

Viscosity of Electrolyte Solutions

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THE search for an equation of fluidity which would account for the variation of viscosity of electrolyte solutions with concentration over a wide range dates back to the early days of solution chemistry. But till now hardly any progress has been achieved in concentrated electrolyte solutions, particularly beyond 0.1 *M*. In this respect the model proposed by Goldsack and Franchetto¹ who based their derivation of the equation of fluidity on the absolute rate theory successfully explains the viscosity results of simple electrolyte in highly concentrated solutions, extending nearly to saturation. Another approach was made by Angell^{2,3} who adopted the equation of fluidity based on the free volume theory of liquids to fused salt mixtures and electrolyte solutions by proposing that the only parameter dependent on the electrolyte concentration is T_0 , the glass transition temperature. Assuming a linear dependence of T_0 on the electrolyte concentrations, N in equivalent per litre, Angell² put forward the following equation of fluidity of electrolyte solution,

$$1/\eta = Ae^{-k'/(N_0 - N)} \quad (1)$$

where, A and k' are two parameters supposed to be independent of composition and N_0 is the hypothetical concentration at which the glass transition would occur.

Roy Choudhury and Majumdar⁴ modified equation (1) by incorporating the condition that $\eta \rightarrow \eta_0$, the viscosity of the solvent as $N \rightarrow 0$, so that it becomes

$$\ln \eta_{rel} = \frac{k'N}{N_0(N_0 - N)} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) has been shown to be valid for the concentration dependence of the viscosity of quaternary ammonium halides⁴⁻⁶ in aqueous solutions for wide range of concentration for suitable values of N_0 . Moreover, this equation in the dilute solution range led to Jones-Dole equation without the Falkenhagen term and one could identify the k'/N_0^2 with the B coefficient of Jones-Dole equation.

In view of these results, it would be worthwhile to test the validity of equation (2) for an electrolyte in a non-aqueous solvent and at several temperatures. We have examined equation (2) with respect to temperature dependence of the viscosity of simple electrolytes, KCl and NaCl in aqueous solutions as well as the concentration dependence of viscosity at a fixed temperature of lithium chloride in *N,N*-dimethylformamide.

Experimental

Potassium chloride (KCl) and sodium chloride (NaCl) were of AnalaR quality and the purity of the samples checked by the determination of chloride volumetrically.

N,N-Dimethylformamide (E. Merck, India) was freshly distilled under reduced pressure before use. The solvent having density 0.9350 g cm⁻³ at 35° compared favourably with the literature value. Stock solutions of the alkali halides were prepared by direct weighing and filtered to remove any suspended impurities and the concentration of the alkali halide determined by titration against standard silver nitrate solution. The solution of desired concentration was made by appropriate dilution with double-distilled water. The solution of lithium chloride in *N,N*-dimethylformamide was made by direct weighing and the desired concentration made by appropriate dilution with freshly distilled *N,N*-dimethylformamide.

All the measurements of density and time of flow were taken in a constant temperature water-bath controlled to ±0.05°. The time of flow was measured in a suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer by a stop watch reading upto 1/10th of a second. A bicapillary pycnometer was employed for the determination of density.

Results and Discussion

Viscosity of KCl and NaCl in aqueous solutions : The viscosity of KCl and NaCl in aqueous solutions were determined over a wide range of concentration extending to saturation at three different temperature, 35, 40 and 45°. It was seen that these data nicely fit equation (2). The plot of ln η_{rel} vs N/(N₀ - N) produces straight line through the origin at the temperatures studied for suitable value of N₀ (Figs. 1 and 2). The value of N₀ was chosen

Fig. 2. Plot of ln η_{rel} vs N/(N₀ - N) for NaCl at different temperature : (○) 35.0, (△) 40.0 and (□) 45.0°.

by trial and error method described earlier⁴. The set of N₀ and k' which produced minimum deviation between observed η_{rel} and those calculated according to equation (2) is accepted as the best choice. These values of N₀ and k' for KCl and NaCl are given in Table 1. It is seen in Table 1 that the value of N₀ increases with temperature.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF N₀ AND k' FOR ELECTROLYTES IN WATER

	Temp. °C	N ₀	k'	k'/N ₀ ²	B*
KCl	35.0	7.2	0.6938	0.0132	0.0098
	40.0	7.8	1.0520	0.0182	(0.0242)
	45.0	9.4	2.0587	0.023	—
NaCl	35.0	19.4	34.76	0.092	0.0900
	40.0	19.9	35.50	0.090	(0.0982)
	45.0	20.2	38.71	0.096	—

* Values of B-coefficient are taken from literature (Ref. 7) and values in parentheses refer to 42.5°.

Fig. 1. Plot of ln η_{rel} vs N/(N₀ - N) for KCl at different temperature : (○) 35.0, (△) 40.0 and (□) 45.0°.

In Table 1 are given the values of k'/N₀² which compare favourably with the B coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation as given in the literature⁷.

Viscosity of LiCl in N,N-dimethylformamide : The viscosity studies of LiCl in *N,N*-dimethylformamide covers a concentration range 0.3-2.5 M at 35°. When the relative viscosity is treated by means of Jones-Dole equation, we find steeply ascending curve as the concentration of lithium chloride increases (Fig. 3). This is not unexpected since it is already known that the Jones-Dole equation has been found to be satisfactory only upto 0.1 M. As the studies of the viscosity in the present investigation begins with a concentration > 0.3 M, it is obvious that the valid concentration range for the application of Jones-Dole equation has been far exceeded. Naturally we treat our data with Angell's equation, rearranged as equation (2). It

is seen that the plot of equation (2) produced a straight line passing through the origin for $N_0 = 27.0$ (Fig. 4). The value of N_0 has been selected

Fig. 3. Jones-Dole plot for LiCl in DMF at 35.0°.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\ln \eta_{rel}$ vs $N/(N_0 - N)$ for LiCl in DMF at 35.0°.

by trial and error method, and the value of N_0 and k' are given in Table 2. Further it is seen that the

TABLE 2—VALUES OF N_0 AND k' FOR LITHIUM CHLORIDE IN DMF AT 35.0°

	N_0	k'	k'/N_0^2
LiCl	27.0	563.92	0.77

value of k'/N_0^2 for LiCl in *N,N*-dimethylformamide is 0.7; this value falls in a similar range for LiCl in other amide solvent⁸, *N*-methylpropionamide and *N*-methylformamide.

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References

1. D. E. GOLDSACK and R. C. FRANCHETTO, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 1442.
2. C. A. ANGELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2793.
3. C. A. ANGELL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, **46**, 4673.
4. K. ROY CHOUDHURY and D. K. MAJUMDAR, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1983, **28**, 23.
5. K. ROY CHOUDHURY and D. K. MAJUMDAR, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1983, **28**, 597.
6. K. ROY CHOUDHURY and D. K. MAJUMDAR, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1981, **29**, 1371.
7. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", 2nd. ed., Butterworths, London, 1959.
8. P. P. RASTOGLI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1970, **43**, 2442.

Spectral Analysis of some α -Benzylmandelic Acids

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HYDROXY acids are very useful in organic synthesis, due largely to the versatility of the hydroxyl group in undergoing a variety of reactions and hence their synthesis is of considerable interest. Baker and Robinson¹ reported that chalcone epoxide on treatment with alkali yields α -benzylmandelic acid after undergoing an initial elimination reaction entailing epoxide ring opening followed by a benzil-benzilic acid type rearrangement. Bharara *et al.*² reported a similar observation in the case of 2-benzylloxychalcone epoxides. However, a systematic spectral analysis of α -benzylmandelic acids has not been reported in the literature. In this note, we report melting point, microanalytical, ir and nmr spectral data of seven α -benzylmandelic acids, prepared^{1,2} by the action of alcoholic alkali (reflux, 4 h) on the appropriate chalcone epoxides. The latter were prepared^{3,4} from the respective chalcones by treatment with alkaline hydrogen peroxide.

- (1)
 a X=Y=H
 b X=p-CH₃; Y=H
 c X=p-Cl; Y=H
 d X=o-Cl; Y=H
 e X=H; Y=p-Cl
 f X=m-Cl; Y=H
 g X=p-CH₃; Y=p-Cl

Reagents: (i) Alcoholic NaOH reflux; H₂O, H⁺.

Some characteristic features of the nmr spectra of the α -benzylmandelic acids are (i) the two methylene protons of the benzyl group are, as expected, non-equivalent and show geminal coupling (J 11-15 Hz), (ii) the protons of the chlorinated aromatic ring in **2c** and **2g** appear as AB doublets instead of the expected AA'BB' pattern, and